

Social media A Age of Surveillance In The Prospect of Artificial Intelligence

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Abstract-

Use of digital gadgets, social media, online games, online shopping platform, e-readings, etc. has become a new normal in the 21st century. Digital gadgets have become a basic component of daily routine. But is this new normal, really affecting us as an individual and society in a positive manner, despite making our day to day lives easier? Estimates suggest that more than 210 million people worldwide suffer from addiction to social media and the internet (Science Direct). This article discusses the issues related to digital addiction by analyzing, reviewing and outlining the effects of digital addiction on individuals and society. A detailed review was conducted, using previous researches which correlated to the issues pertaining to this research. An explanation of digital addiction, its classification, symptoms and cures has been established under this article. This article tries to explain the dangerous impacts of digital addiction on the individuals and on society as a whole, covering various aspects such as health, social well-being, etc.

Keywords: Digital Addiction, Digital Devices, Social Media, Technology Addiction, Excessive Usage, Digital free life, Internet, Addiction.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the 21st century, as the world is moving towards advancement through various technologies, all invented by human beings for the betterment of life, there are certain technologies which are affecting human lives adversely even when these technologies are a life savior.

In this era of artificial intelligence, real time collaboration, knowledge management, etc. we, human beings are falling into the trap of “Digitalization” or we can say “Digital Addiction”.

How? Let us understand by learning about its meaning first.

Digital Addiction as per United Brains means “A harmful dependence on digital media and devices such as smartphones, video games and computers.”

As per the recent reports by datareportal, total active users of internet in January 2023, across the globe were 5.16 billion, along with 4.76 billion active users of social media. In addition to this, around 6 hours 37 minutes are spent by worldwide population, between the age 16 to 64, on the internet.

The following image clearly shows the data of device ownership globally.

Source- GWI (Q3 – 2022)

The magnitude or severity of such addiction depends on various factors such as time spent on digital gadgets, social media, online games, online shopping platform, e-readings, etc.

As the impact of digital addiction is not same on all age groups, in this research we have tried to identify as many impacts as possible that digital addiction has over various age groups covering various aspects such as health, social well-being, etc. Such addiction can also lead to criminal activities by the users; we have tried to throw some light on such crimes as well through our research.

II. LITERATUREREVIEW

Beard, K. W. (2002)

Internet addiction: current status and implications for employees.” The paper suggest the Internet is a new technology that has influenced the world and has provided many benefits to its users. At the same time, however, this influence has had negative ramifications. Some people are becoming preoccupied with the Internet, are unable to control their use of this technology, and are jeopardizing their employment and personal relationships. Internet addiction has been proposed as an explanation for uncontrollable, damaging use of this technology. Warning signs that an employee is having difficulty controlling his or her Internet use are reviewed.

Kanwal Nalwa et al (2003)

“Internet addiction in students: A cause of Concern “paper highlights the dramatic increase use of internet in recent years had led to internet addiction. In this study teen age students participated from India .they divide student into two groups ,they found result like delay other work ,more time spend on internet, loss sleep due to late night logons, feel life boring without internet.

Sharmitha Krishnamurthy et al (2012)

study on the impact of mobile phone and internet use on self-reported behavioral changes. A descriptive survey using convenient sampling technique conducted among 542 undergraduate students of Udupi district, to find the impact of mobile phone and internet use on self-reported behavioral changes revealed that, 78 (14.4%) subjects reported of having mobile phone problematic use and 39 (7.2%) with internet addiction behavior. Also 146 (27%) subjects reported problem in their social interaction with the internet use. Gender was found to have significant association with internet and mobile phone use.

Arun Vijay Paul.RChellavelGanapthi.K Duraimurugan .M, Abirami. V, Elizabeth Reji (2015)

They conducted study on The excessive and inappropriate use of Internet is a growing concern in the current tech-savy World. The youth are particularly vulnerable to this problem which may

ruin their very critical academic career. The aim of this study is to determine the prevalence of Internet Addiction pattern and to analyze the associated factors among the college students from various education field. The internet addiction problem among students should gain attention and it is time to evolve an comprehensive intervention approach to promote and safe Internet use.

RESEARCH GAP

Although there has been many researches done on various aspects of digital addiction but no concrete research is available on the impacts of digital addiction on people with different age groups and how they differ based on various factors. We have tried to focus on small aspects which can lead to digital addiction in any person. We have even tried to establish a relationship between digital addiction and cybercrimes which are happening in the world.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

1. To understand the meaning of digital addiction, because before moving ahead with the impacts it is necessary to understand the meaning of digital addiction.
2. To understand the factors that lead to digital addiction in the people of various age groups.
3. To establish a relationship between digital addiction and crimes.
4. To cover the possible methods of coping up with digital addiction.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- To Are women able to raise their voice for divorce in rural areas?
- What issues do women in rural areas have when getting divorced?

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

To conduct this research we used Search Methodology to come up to the reasons and the solutions for digital addiction in people of different age groups. Because the first publication on such topic was made in the year 2012 thus we included papers from 2012 till 2022. We used Google scholar for searching these research papers. The terms that we used to search were, ‘ Digital Addiction’, ‘Internet Addiction’, ‘Digital Devices’, ‘Social Media’, ‘Technology Addiction’, etc. The inclusion and exclusion involved;

- a) Searching on Google Scholar.

b) Written in English.

c) Analysis considering the general contents of relevant papers.

d) Classification of papers according to various aspects like symptoms, causes, and coping methods.

IV. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Whenever we talk about Digitalization than we think about mobile phones, computers, internet, database, etc. which has now become a part of our daily routine as all of them helps us in a smooth and easy going life by making our day to day tasks easier and quicker.

It has become so easy to share a message to thousands of people on a single click, to make and receive payments in seconds, to access to rarely available books in digital form, to easily shop from our favorite brands of clothing to our groceries.

But do we ever think of the cost that we pay for all these luxuries? These luxuries might cost us our mental peace, health, social well-being, etc. How? Let's understand.

In today's world when everything is available to us by internet and digital gadgets, we have become so much habitual of these gadgets and internet that instead of just doing our routine task and keeping away these gadgets we get stuck to them long hours just to entertain ourselves and pass our time. This can't be only said for young generation but this habit can be seen in the people of all the age groups such as kids, teenagers, adults and old age people.

The *American Society of Addiction Medicine* (ASAM)¹ released a definition of addiction as a chronic brain disorder, officially proposing for the first time that addiction is not limited to substance use.

V. CAUSES

To understand this better let us first understand that the causes of getting addicted to these digital devices are different on the people with different age groups. To break it more we will be dividing these people in 3 different age groups:

- Kids (4-12years)
- Teenagers and adults (13-45years)

¹American Society of Addiction Medicine. Public Policy Statement: Definition of Addiction. 2011 [cited 2011 August

- Old (50 years and above)

All these groups are assumed to be suffering from digital addiction but the causes are different for all of them.

Causes of Digital Addiction in kids

Parental Habits

Parental habits play a major role in increasing the digital addiction in kids. As it is said that kids learn what they see, today the parenting has changed a lot. Young parents have started to provide digital gadgets on the name of luxury which ultimately leads in digital addiction in kids. Sometimes this can be seen that to stop a kid from crying parents give them mobile phones, shows them TV, asks them to play games on computer, etc. this behavior at the end might lead to digital addiction in kids. This might help the parents for some hours but they do not understand the long term significance of these small activities.

Lack of academic involvement

Now-a-days, even school have become digitally advanced, which somehow helps in providing quality education the students but such advancement should be limited to certain age groups. Today small kids are taught on digital boards, given home works which are to be done on computers, tablets, exams are taken online, activities involves recording videos, audios, etc. These activities affects adversely on the minds of small kids who are in their initial age of learning.

No boundaries and set rules

Today's kids are free to do anything that they are willing to do. Parents, guardians, teachers on the name of providing liberty and freedom to kids allow kids to play online games, enjoy screen time, using mobile phones etc. Freedom is important and must be given to the kids but not on the cost of their health.

Lack of friends

Today's kids lacks when it comes to socialization. This leads to kids not having any friends with whom they can interact, play with. When kids do not have any friends they indulge in getting addicted to digital devices. Loneliness in kids can also be observed in today's era.

Today instead of playing with friends kids are more interested in playing on mobile phones, computers, etc. Today kids have more friends on Facebook rather than in their real-life.

Easy access to newer technologies

Now-a-days kids are aware of newer technologies and are always keen to learn them, be it a new game or a new application or a new trend on instagram/snapchat/facebook.

But ever wondered why they are so fascinated by these new technologies? Because, they have an easy access to these technologies. This easy access has somehow indulged kids towards digital addiction.

Causes of Digital Addiction in Teenagers and Adults

Social Security

Today's youth wants to be recognized by everyone. They want to tell the world about their life, what they do, what they eat, where they go, with whom they go, etc. Social presence on the social media platforms has become an important part of their lives. One is not given a good social recognition in the society if they do not have any presence on social media platforms.

Such hunger for social security has increased digital addiction in the youth mainly teenagers.

Boredom and loneliness

Even after having so much of social recognition and online friends, today's youth experience boredom and loneliness. Such boredom again pushes the person to indulge in some kind of online activity be it online gaming, watching videos, online shopping, reading e-books, etc.

Thus this all result in engaging them maximum hours on digital devices, which by the time become an addiction.

Hunger for information

Although this point might surprise some people but hunger for information is not an advantage in all the cases. Today all the information is available on the internet. Anyone who is interested to get information of any sort will go on the internet and surf for hours looking for what information they want. Having knowledge about things is not bad but when it costs your health it is surely not important. People now a day wants to be connected with the world.

Sexual Desires

Once a person attains an age of 13 years, he/she go through a lot of physical transformation in their bodies. After attaining certain age some people develop a keen interest towards sex and related aspects. In a recent study conducted in Iran, approximately half of the participants stated

that they use the internet for access to inappropriate content such as pornography.²

Causes of Digital Addiction in Old Age People

Permanent Accessibility with Family

Old age people are likely to be more attached to their family members; they want to have an access wherein they can connect with any of them whenever they want. Today all the members of the families are busy in their own lives so it becomes easy for the old age people to be connected with them on any digital platform.

Leisure Activities

As people attain an age where they are not burdened with any responsibilities and have a lot of free time to enjoy, then they indulge in leisure activities. Leisure activities also include watching movies, reading books, online shopping, etc. If any person is involved in such activities then there are high chances of them getting addicted. They are always up for new things which they can see, learn or adapt.

Retirement Boredom

Once a person gets retired, people assume that they have all the time in the world to do anything that they want which is true to an extent but they are not aware that there is a term called retirement boredom where a person who is now retired has actually nothing to do except his daily routine tasks. They somewhere feel this boredom and to overcome this boredom many people indulge themselves in using digital devices, which ultimately results in digital addiction. As now we have discussed the causes of digital addiction on the people with different age groups let's turn our focus towards the impact that digital addiction have on people. As we can bifurcate the causes of this addiction but the impact is somehow same on all age groups.

Impacts of Digital Addiction

Health Issues:

- **Physical Health**

²Norouzi L, Arbabi A, Jamali M. The effect of internet usage on relations between members of the Iran Family in Tehran City. *World Fam Med J.* 2017;99:1-5.

Digital Addiction plays a significant role in depleting the physical health of the person suffering from it. A study have found that it can have adverse effects of the physical health of the person. As the person spends most of his time using interne, mobile phones, computers, etc. they spend less time on their physical fitness which ultimately lead in agitation, weight loss/gain, loss of interest in other physical activities, etc.

A study says that digital addiction can lead to massive effect on physical health, the common ones being a pain, stiffness in arms and joints, dry and strained eyes, back-pain, neck-pain leading to headache, sleeping disorder, extreme hyperactivity, excessive talkativeness, decreases in hygiene, and eating disorders, all of which have further impacts one's physical health deleteriously.³

The body of the person becomes lazy which instigates to person to become more inactive.

- **Mental Health**

In a study ⁴ on young adolescents, it was found that about 74.5% were moderate (average) users and 0.7% were found to be addicts. Those with excessive use of Internet had high scores on anxiety, depression, and anxiety depression.

As due to digital addiction, the mental health of the adults and old age people are more at a risk as they are more involved in socialization which is an important factor that leads to digital addiction.

▪ **Increased Isolation**

Because people spend more time online or on digital platforms, they tend to becomes anti-social as rarely involve in socializing in real life with real people. This might sometimes lead to loneliness and boredom.

▪ **Career obstruction (poor performance in school or at work)**

When we talk about adults and school/college going student, then they are also very much affected by the excessive use of digital devices. Due to hours of use of smartphones, internet, computers, employed people as well as school/college going students are adversely affected. They are unable to focus on their work/studies, pass time when the work is to be done and then gets depressed once the time passes.

Poor performance in school/college and at work has been a result of digital addiction.

³Aderinto, Nicholas MBBS, International Journal of Surgery: Global Health 5(6): p e88, November 2022

⁴Goel D, Subramanyam A, Kamath R. A study on the prevalence of internet addiction and its association with psychopathology in Indian adolescents. *Indian J Psychiatry*. 2013

Social Life:

Today everyone has their own identity on social media platforms, such identities are never same as the real lives. Everyone wants to impress others by their social media profiles. In this world of show-off it has become important to gen-z's to be as active as they can be on social media, which means they spend more time on social media. This thirst of having a perfect profile can sometime leads to depression as there in no criteria for having a perfect profile, you have to just follow the trends on Instagram, Facebook, Snapchat and other social media platforms.

These trends change within a small period of time, which sometimes put pressure on people to flow with the trend resulting in hours of spending their valuable time on social media platforms. The hunger for likes on photos, videos shared by people on social media is has increased so much that it has become a part of adults and teenagers and even kids in some cases where they spend maximum time of their day on social media.

Low quality of life

Digital addiction leads to low quality of life as when any person of any age group becomes a digital addict, it is sure that he/she will suffer from some of the condition that comes with this addiction, which somewhere degrades the quality of life.

Effect on interpersonal relationships

A new study⁵ has found that married couple's relationships are being damaged by the excessive use of smartphones. The study "Switch Off," surveyed 2,000 customers in various cities in India. The survey was conducted by Cybermedia Research and was powered by smartphone manufacturer Vivo.

The study found that 67 % of respondents admitted to using their smartphones even while spending time with their spouse. This excessive usage is having a negative impact on relationships. Around 89% of respondents say they spend less time engaging in relaxed conversation with their loved ones than they would like. 88 per cent of the respondents claimed that excessive use of smartphones is harming their relationships.

Involvement in crimes

There is a significance relationship between digital addiction and crimes (mostly cybercrimes). As we already discussed that social media presence has become very important for people these

⁵ <https://www.vivo.com/in/about-vivo/news/74-parents-confess>

days. To mark their presence people, use various tactics like posting pictures or videos, chatting with people, sharing each other's thoughts via written posts or mails and even in comments.

We know our laws has given us maximum freedom as it can to express our thoughts, views on social media about other persons or places or events, etc.

But people these days are seen misusing this freedom by expressing their views in such a way that it can hurt someone's sentiments.

There are even cases where crime happens because of some tiff going on because of some issue over any social media platform.

As per a survey by Statista in 2017, there were over 300 cases of cybercrime related to social media across India. This was a marginal spike in crime cases compared to the previous year when there were just over 150 cases of social media cybercrime reported in the country.⁶

VI. RESEARCH FINDINGS

Causes and impact of digital addiction on the people with different age groups.

The main area of this research finding was to highlight the causes and impacts of digital addiction on the people with different age groups. As we noted that the cause are bifurcated as per the different age groups but the impacts of digital addiction are almost same for all age groups.

Relationship between Digital addiction and crimes.

The research was also conducted to identify the relationship between digital addiction and crime. And we found out that there are crimes, majorly cybercrimes, the root cause of which are digital platforms.

VII. CONCLUSION

As we have now studied the impact of Digital Addiction on people we can draw some conclusion and provide some recommendations on the same:

Access to preferred activities must be restricted.

This is a major thing that is to be done by each and every individual. They should put some restrictions on the access to their preferred activities. This will help them in spending lesser time

⁶<https://www.statista.com/statistics/875906/india-number-of-cyber-crimes-related-to-social-media/>

on digital gadgets. Even in offices there should be a policy wherein the employees have to stop using the screen after a fixed period of time. Kids must be restricted to use any kind of screen after a particular time period.

Inclination towards fitness

Everyone should move their focus towards fitness. It is important for a smooth function of our body. It is to be understood that our body needs some kind of physical activity to be active. Digital addiction does not allow a person to indulge in any physical activity as their mind and body are always inactive, depressed and lazy.

Involvement in old-school activities

The era when there were no or very rarely people have mobile phones, computers, tablets, access to internet, was the golden era when it comes to digital addiction as people does not have any easy access to these, they were more involved in physical activities, there were so many types of entertainment channels present at that time which does not need internet, phone or any other gadgets. We understand it is not easy to stay away from all these in this era but people must try to adopt old school activities wherein self-control is what is needed.

Restriction on social media

It is a high time when our government has to realize that there should be some policy or law wherein a restriction is put on the use of social media, today in the name of freedom of speech, people are free to comment on anything in any way. This may lead to hurting sentiments of any person, religion, faith etc.

There should be some law which restricts people on expressing their feelings in such a manner that it can hurt some other person's sentiments, faith religious feelings etc.

Medical Help

People suffering from digital addiction should be treated as normal patients. It should not be thought as an act of shame, as it is thought in today's society. Such medical help should be easily accessible to all so that if anyone is in a need of such help can get the access of it easily.

VIII. REFERENCES

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